

Mixed ligand complexes : stabilities and reactivities

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The investigations of stabilities and reactivities of coordination complexes have been actively pursued at several research centres in this country. A brief review is presented here in this area with emphasis on our own work. The ligand substitution dynamics at several metal centres both in aqueous and mixed solvent media, isomerisation reactions and the reactions of coordinated ligands form the general theme of this review.

During the last five decades there has been tremendous upsurge of interest on the study of stabilities and reactivities of mixed ligand complexes of metal ions. Attention has been focussed on the coordination complexes with possible variation of metal ions, ligands (monodentate and multidentate) and solvent media. From the mechanistic standpoints, ligand substitution, redox and isomerisation reactions of coordination complexes have been examined intensely. The complexes of cobalt(III), chromium(III), platinum(II,IV), rhodium(III), ruthenium(II,III), iridium(III) which undergo comparatively slow substitution reactions have proved to be useful models. With the advent of sophisticated techniques greater emphasis has been laid on the study of labile metal ion complexes in the recent years.

The inertness or lability of a complex on kinetics ground is a measure of the time-scale of its reaction. Hence one of the important aspects of kinetic study is time resolution. In the days of Ostwald, Wilhelmy time resolution to >1 s could be achieved by conventional techniques. It was, however, upgraded in the latter years to 10^{-3} s by the *stopped flow* and from 10^{-3} to 10^{-6} s by early *flash photolysis* techniques. Further improvement to study reactions occurring in the time-scale 10^{-5} to 10^{-9} s could be made by the *chemical relaxation* method. The time resolution 10^{-9} – 10^{-15} s has been possible in the recent years by application of lasers. This has opened up the possibilities of generating/detecting the transient species and studying their reactivities. Despite this technological advancement directly elucidating the structure of the transition state of any chemical reaction still remains as the most baffling task.

Several research centres have sprung up in our country in the last three decades where investigation of the rates and mechanisms of reactions of coordination compounds

are being actively pursued. The purpose of this article is to project briefly the contributions from different laboratories in our country in this area during the last decade. This review is, however, not exhaustive but gives a glimpse of research activities. Our emphasis is focussed largely on the ligand substitution, isomerisation and reactions of coordinated ligands.

Ligand substitution reactions

Solvent exchange :

The ligand substitution reactions of metal complexes is a widely covered area. The aqua metal ions serve as reference substrates and the kinetics of water exchange serve as the reference reaction. This could be generalised as the solvent exchange reactions of the solvated metal ion (eq. 1),

In eq.(1) S and S' denote the bound and exchanging solvent molecules, respectively. The kinetics of water exchange reactions of the aqua metal ions have been investigated most extensively. It may be noted that the rate constants span ~18 order or magnitude (Table 1). The trivalent metal ions like Fe^{3+} , Ga^{3+} undergo extensive hydrolysis. Their monohydroxo-species are much more labile to solvent exchange than the corresponding hexa-aqua cations. The mechanism of solvent exchange may be dissociative (D), associative (A) or interchange process with predominant M-S bond breaking (I_d) or M-S' bond formation (I_a) (S, S' = H_2O for water exchange). Based on the activation parameter data the solvent exchange reactions of $Be(S_4)^{2+}$ is believed to shift from $D-I_d-I_a-A^1$ on varying the nature and bulkiness of the coordinated and exchanging solvent molecules.

Table 1. Solvent exchange rate and activation parameters for some solvated metal ions at 25^oa*

Metal ion	Solvent	k_{ex} s ⁻¹	ΔH^\ddagger kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔS^\ddagger J K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹
Li ⁺ , Na ⁺ , K ⁺ , Cs ⁺	H ₂ O	~10 ⁹		
Ca ²⁺ , Ba ²⁺ , Sr ²⁺	H ₂ O	~(6-9) × 10 ⁸		
Mg ²⁺	H ₂ O	~10 ⁶	~57	
	CH ₃ OH	4.7 × 10 ³	70	58
Be ²⁺	H ₂ O	2.1 × 10 ³	35	-63
V ²⁺	H ₂ O	90	69	23
Al ³⁺	H ₂ O	0.17,	113	117
		16	65	0
Ga ³⁺	H ₂ O	1.8 × 10 ³ ,	26	-92
		7.6 × 10 ³	69	42
In ³⁺	H ₂ O	4.0 × 10 ⁴	19	-96
Ti ³⁺	H ₂ O	1.0 × 10 ⁵	26	-63
V ³⁺	H ₂ O	1.0 × 10 ³ ,	37	-62
		1.6 × 10 ³	26	-96
VO ²⁺	H ₂ O	8 × 10 ² ,	56	-8
		5 × 10 ²	57	-4
V ²⁺	H ₂ O	90	68	23
Cr ²⁺	H ₂ O	>10 ⁸		
Cr ³⁺	H ₂ O	5.8 × 10 ⁻⁷ ,	113	42
		4.3 × 10 ⁻⁷	109	1.2
	NH ₃	6 × 10 ⁻⁵		
Mn ²⁺	H ₂ O	3.1 × 10 ⁷ ,	34	12
		4 × 10 ⁷ ,	31	4
		2.6 × 10 ⁷	33	6
Fe ²⁺	H ₂ O	3.2 × 10 ⁶	32	-12
Fe ³⁺	H ₂ O	1.6 × 10 ^{2a}		
FeOH ²⁺	H ₂ O	4 × 10 ^{5 a}		
Co ³⁺	H ₂ O	~0.1		
Co ²⁺	H ₂ O	2.2 × 10 ⁶	43	21
	NH ₃	7.2 × 10 ⁶	47	41
	CH ₃ OH	1.8 × 10 ⁴	57	29
	DMF	3.9 × 10 ⁵	57	54
		2.3 × 10 ⁵	30	-41
Ni ²⁺	H ₂ O	3.0 × 10 ⁴	45	17
	NH ₃	4.7 × 10 ⁴	42	-13
	CH ₃ OH	1.0 × 10 ³	66	33
	DMF	7.7 × 10 ³	39	-37
Cu ²⁺	H ₂ O	>10 ⁸		
Zn ²⁺	H ₂ O	~10 ⁸		
Cd ²⁺	H ₂ O	>10 ⁸		

Table-1 (contd.)

Hg ²⁺	H ₂ O	~2 × 10 ⁹		
Rh ³⁺	H ₂ O	2.2 × 10 ⁻⁵	136	56
		(at 64°)		
(La-Lu) ³⁺	H ₂ O	~10 ⁸		

*"Coordination Chemistry", ACS Monograph 174 (Plenum), Vol. 2, 1978, p. 5; *Prog. Inorg. Chem.*, 1997, **13**, 114.

^aH. W. Dodgen, G. Liu and J. P. Hunt, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1981, **20**, 2002; M. Grant and R. B. Jordan, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1981, **20**, 55.

Substitution reactions of aquametal ion complexes :

Aquametal ions and monodentate ligands : Monodentate ligands react reversibly with aqua cations via a two-step process as proposed by Eigen, Wilkins and Tamme²,

The formation of the outer-sphere complex, $\{M(OH_2)_6^{n+}, L^{m-}\}$, is diffusion-controlled. The rate of reversible formation of $ML^{(n-m)+}$ is then given by eq. (3),

$$d[ML^{(n-m)+}]/dt = K_{os} k_1 [M^{n+}] [L^{m-}] - k_{-1} [ML^{(n-m)+}] \quad (3)$$

when the concentration of the ion-pair is negligible as compared to $[M^{n+}]$ and $[L^{m-}]$ {or K_{os} is to be replaced by $K_{os}/(1 + K_{os} [A])$ for substantial ion-pairing, $[A] = [M^{n+}]$ or $[L^{m-}]$ when $[M^{n+}] \ll [L^{m-}]$ or $[L^{m-}] \ll [M^{n+}]$, respectively}. K_{os} is amenable to measurements only when the anation of the aqua cation is sufficiently slow. Most aqua cations undergo fast anation (see Table 1 for the water exchange rate constants). In those cases k_1 , the ligand/H₂O exchange rate constant, is calculated from the formation rate constant ($k_f = K_{os} k_1$) using an estimated value of K_{os} from Fuoss equation (eq. 4),

$$K_{os} = (4\pi Na^3/3000) \exp(-b) \exp(bK_p a / (1 + K_p a)) \quad (4)$$

$$K_p = [(8\pi Ne_0^2/1000 Dk_B T) I]^{1/2}$$

where, a is the centre-to-centre distance between M^{n+} and L^{m-} in the ion-pair, $b = Z_M Z_L e_0^2 / Da k_B T$, k_B is the Boltzmann constant, e_0 the electronic charge (esu), D the relative permittivity, T the temperature (K) and I the ionic strength. Value of a is usually chosen as 4-5 Å. Fuoss theory predicts the values of K_{os} (298°, $I = 0.1$ mol dm⁻³) as 87, 13, 2, 1 and 0.3 for +2, -3; +2, -2; +1, -2; +1, -1; $p, 0$ ($p =$ any charge between +3 to -3) charge type association. Experimentally significant ion-pairing is also not observed for

tigated recently. The hydroxamic acids, dimethylglyoxime, ferron have been used to examine the kinetics and mechanism of reactions with metal ions like iron(III), cobalt(II), copper(II), uranium(VI)⁹.

Recently Malhotra *et al.*¹⁰ have investigated the kinetics and mechanism of complexation of Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} with a number of amino acids and related biologically important ligands. A comparative study of the kinetics of complexation of Ni^{II} with 2-aminomethylbenzimidazole (AMB)¹¹ and 2-aminoethylbenzimidazole (AEB)¹² has been reported. Both neutral and mono-protonated ligands react to yield the final chelated product, the latter with loss of a proton,

At 25.0° ($I = 0.3 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) $k_f^L(k_f^{\text{HL}}) = 6.3 \pm 0.2 \times 10^3$ ($3.0 \pm 0.3 \times 10^2$) and $2.2 \pm 0.2 \times 10^3$ (33 ± 10) $\text{dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ for AMB and AEB, respectively. The relatively lower values of the rate constants for AEB (AEBH⁺) are ascribed to the chelate ring size as both the ligands do not differ in basicity significantly. This is tenable in terms of the *chelation controlled* mechanism at least for AEB in which case NiL²⁺ has a six-membered chelate ring. The kinetics of formation of the mixed ligand complexes of Cu(biguanide)²⁺ with bipyridyl, 1,10-phenanthroline, glycine, alanine¹³ and of (NTA)M(II) (M(II) = Co, Ni) with SCN⁻, bipyridyl, and 1,10-phenanthroline have also been reported^{14a}. The ternary complexes of nickel(II)-2-aminomethylbenzimidazole with 3-nitrosalicylate and *cis*-(ammine)(3-nitrosalicylato)-bis(ethylenediamine)cobalt(III) displayed slow structural isomerism in aqueous medium^{14b} attributable to the influence of steric effect of the ligands on the thermodynamic stabilities of the involved complexes. The reversible formation of ternary complexes of Ni^{II}(L)(H₂O)_{6-n} with N₅Co^{III}(O₂C-2-pyridine) (N₅ = 5NH₃, tetraethylenepentamine; L = H₂O, bipyridyl, iminodiacetate, and nitrilotriacetate) has been studied recently by Dash *et al.*^{14c}. The interesting aspect of this study is that the mechanism of formation of the ternary complexes shifts from *I*_d to *chelation controlled* process with the decrease of the available sites for coordination in Ni^{II}(L)(OH₂)_{6-n}. The ternary complexes serve as useful models for many biological reactions.

Binuclear complexes :

Binuclear complexes are formed when two metal ions (M₁, M₂) are bridged by a common ligand,

Such species are involved as intermediates in the *trans*-metallation, serve as precursors in the inner-sphere redox reactions of metal complexes and in several metal ion catalysed reactions. Multidentate ligands bound to inert metal centres and still with available donor sites have proved good complexing agents^{15,16a-h}. The dicarboxylates, substituted salicylates, amino acids and aminopolycarboxylates bound to a N₅Co³⁺ moiety via the carboxylate group have been used as possible substrates for the binuclear complexation reactions. The kinetics and mechanism of the binuclear complexation of several metal ions such as Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Be^{II}, Al^{III}, Ga^{III} and Fe^{III} have been investigated with possible variations of charge, basicity, chelate ring size, structure and dentate nature of the ligands. A typical reaction is depicted below :

The formation of the mono-bonded intermediate (A) and its subsequent transformation to the chelate form (B) are likely to take place at different time scales. But these steps have not been resolved yet. In every case the reaction studied by stopped flow technique displayed monophasic behaviour. Protonation of the ligational site considerably reduced its complexing rate or totally made the ligand inert to complex with aqua metal ions, the hydrolysed species MOHⁿ⁺ reacted equally efficiently with protonated ligands. It is interesting to note that Be(OH₂)₄²⁺ failed to complex with oxalatopentaamminecobalt(III) while its reaction with (3-NO₂-salicylato)pentaamminecobalt(III) was facile, the metal ion being chelated by the salicylate moiety as evidenced by spectroscopic and kinetic measurements. The rate and activation parameter data for this reaction when compared with those for the water exchange reaction of Be(OH₂)₄²⁺ indicate the possibility of *I*_a mechanism. A comparative study of the kinetics of reversible complexation of Ni^{II} with pyridine-2-carboxylatopentaamminecobalt(III) and pyridine-3-carboxylatopentaamminecobalt(III) proved informative to

decide the mechanism; the chelate ring closure clearly controls the rate-determining step in the formation of the binuclear complex of the former. A contrasting feature is that the dissociation of M(II) from the binuclear species is strongly catalysed by H⁺ for Co^{II} and is H⁺-independent for Ni^{II}; H⁺ is likely to be involved if Co^{II}-N bond-breaking is rate-limiting in the dissociation of the binuclear species.

The chelate ring closure and NH proton dissociation are concerted in the kinetics of complexation of (NH₃)₅CoNTA (NTA = nitrilotriacetate) with bivalent metal ions. Accordingly, general base catalysis has been observed in the complexation by Ni^{II}¹⁵. For the trivalent metal ions, however, the first bond formation between M³⁺ and the dangling carboxylate function is rate-limiting. The mechanism is essentially I_d for the MOH²⁺ species while it may be I_a for M(OH₂)₆³⁺.

Aminopolycarboxylates and multidentate ligand systems :

The reactions of CN⁻ with 1,2-diaminopropanetetraacetatoferrate(III), hydroxypentacyanoferrate(III), Fe₂HPDTA(OH)₂ and bis[4-(2-pyridylazo)(resorcinol)]ferrate(III) have been investigated by Nigam *et al.*¹⁷. They have shown that hydroxopentacyanoferrate(III) is formed when Fe^{III} complex of triethylenetetraminehexaacetic acid and 2-hydroxy-1,3-diaminopropanetetraacetic acid react with CN⁻ in excess. Naik and Nigam^{17d} have tested *linear free energy relationships* for the kinetics of ligand substitution of hydroxopentacyanoferrate(III) and monohydroxoaminopolycarboxylatoiron(III).

The reactions of (*N,N'*-ethylenedisalicylamidato)-nickel(II) with EDTA⁴⁻ (*N,N,N',N'*-ethylenediaminetetraacetate) and CDTA⁴⁻ (*trans*-cyclohexane-1,2-diamine-*N,N,N',N'*-tetraacetate) have been investigated in borate buffer (pH = 9.0–9.7, 25°)¹⁸. The reaction scheme is delineated as follows

The reactivity order, Ni(H₂L) > Ni(HL)⁻ > NiL²⁻ is valid. Steric factors are important for CDTA. The study has been extended to *N,N'*-ethylenedisalicylamidatocopper(II). The diamide ligand complexed to Cu^{II}(CuL) undergoes Cu^{II}-in-

duced deprotonation with pK₁ = 7.34 and pK₂ = 8.82 (30°, I = 0.12 mol dm⁻³, 45% ethanol + water)^{19a}. The steric effects on the rates and mechanism of the reversible formation of Ni^{II}-complexes of 2-imidazoleazobenzene, 2,2'-biimidazole and 2,2'-bibenzimidazole have been examined tently by Dash *et al.*^{19b}. In a recent study, Dash and Mishra^{19c} have also shown that the corresponding Fe^{III}-complex, *N,N'*-ethylenedisalicylamidatoiron(III), undergoes the coordinated amide deprotonation via two successive steps catalysed by bases. The kinetics of replacement of coordinated ethylenediamine in Cr(en)₃³⁺ by bis(2-aminoethyl)-amino-*N,N,N',N',N''*-pentaacetate²⁰, ternary complexes of (NTA)Ni(OH₂)⁺ with amino acids²¹, multidentate ligand exchange kinetics involving (tetraethylenepentamine)-nickel(II) and diethylenetriaminepentaacetic acid or 1,2-propylenedinitrilotetraacetic acid have been reported²².

Solvolytic reactions :

HalogenoamineM(III) complexes : The halogenoamine complexes of cobalt(III), chromium(III), rhodium(III) and ruthenium(III) have played a central role in elucidating the mechanism of substitution at the metal centres. The solvolytic reactions of such complexes have been studied extensively,

Such substrates with at least one NH proton undergo fast base-catalysed hydrolysis. This has been ascribed to the strong labilising action of the amido base generated by the OH⁻-promoted deprotonation of the coordinated amine. Most of the evidences of the amido base formation by the strongly basic amine complexes of Co^{II} and Cr^{III} in aqueous medium are kinetic in nature (pK_{NH} > 15 for the coordinated amine in aqueous medium). However, complexes of weakly basic amines, such as aniline, imidazole, benzimidazole, and 2-aminothiazole have been shown to undergo deprotonation in mildly alkaline medium. It has been established beyond doubt that the amido bases are the reactive species in the base hydrolysis of the amine complexes. For a typical cobalt(III) complex the generally accepted S_{N1}cb mechanism of base hydrolysis is depicted as

The formation of the amido conjugate base may also be rate-

limiting for suitable complexes. Duality of mechanism, and stereochemical consequences have lively impact on the base hydrolysis of octahedral acidoamineM(III) complexes to pursue it further. Search for the transient intermediates supposed to be involved in the base hydrolysis of such complexes continues.

The substrates $[\text{Co}(\text{picdien})\text{X}]^{2+}$ and $[\text{Co}(\text{picditn})\text{X}]^{2+}$ ($\text{X} = \text{Cl}, \text{Br}, \text{NO}_2, \text{NCS}, \text{N}_3$, picdien = 1,9-bis(2'-pyridyl)-2,5,8-triazanonane, picditn = 1,11-bis(2'-pyridyl)-2,6,10-triazaundecane)²³ undergo unusually fast base hydrolysis. Amine proton exchange occurs much faster than the ligand substitution in basic medium supporting $S_{\text{N}1}$ cb mechanism. The real cause of the unusual reactivities of these complexes still remains concealed.

The base catalysed hydrolysis of $\text{cis}(\text{-en})_2\text{Co}(\text{B})\text{X}^{2+}$ ($\text{B} = \text{imidazole}, N\text{-methylimidazole}, \text{benzimidazole}, \text{X} = \text{Cl}, \text{Br}$) have been reported²⁴. The reactivities of the coordinated benzimidazolato and imidazolato complexes have been compared. The rate dependence on the leaving groups and the nonlabile ligands are consistent with the $S_{\text{N}1}$ cb mechanism. The electron displacement properties of N-coordinated imidazolato and benzimidazolato enhance the pK_{NH} of the coordinated ethylenediamine, the effect being more significant for the former anion. Based on the analysis of the activation entropy data in terms of a dissociative activation model for the conjugate base, it has been suggested that configurational changes at the cobalt(III) centre most likely occur in the transition state. Competition experiment with N_3^- has shown that the presumed five-coordinate intermediate is efficiently scavenged by this anion. The rates and activation parameters of the base hydrolysis of benzimidazole and benzimidazolato species of $\beta_2(\text{trien})(\text{benzimidazole})\text{-CoCl}^{2+}$ are fully consistent with the $S_{\text{N}1}$ cb mechanism²⁵. However, it is interesting to note that the benzimidazole species reacted 40 times faster than its conjugate base analogue, $\beta_2(\text{trien})(\text{benzimidazole-1})\text{CoCl}^+$. This contrasting feature is a consequence of the pK_{NH} perturbation effect, the coordinated benzimidazolato enhancing the pK_{NH} of the trien ligand more effectively than its conjugate acid (i.e. benzimidazole).

The base hydrolysis of $\text{cis}(\text{-bromo})(2\text{-aminothiazole})\text{bis}(\text{ethylenediamine})\text{cobalt(III)}^{26}$ in the range of $[\text{OH}^-] = 4.45 \times 10^{-3} - 99.45 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ ($I = 0.1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) deviated from second order kinetics :

$$k_{\text{obs}} = K_{\text{cb}} k_{\text{cb}} [\text{OH}^-] / (1 + K_{\text{cb}} [\text{OH}^-]) \quad (17)$$

At 25° ($I = 0.1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$), $k_{\text{cb}} = 374 \pm 66 \text{ s}^{-1}$, $\Delta H^\ddagger = 46 \pm 5 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$, $\Delta S^\ddagger = -39 \pm 28 \text{ J K}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$; $K_{\text{cb}} = 10.0 \pm 1.0 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$, $\Delta H^\circ = 22 \pm 8 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$, $\Delta S^\circ = 95 \pm 29 \text{ J K}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$. The coordinated thiazoleamine is a stronger acid ($pK_{\text{NH}} = 12.8 \pm 0.1$) than any primary amine coordinated to cobalt(III). This is in keeping with the pronounced effect of coordination. The conjugate base aquates 10^7 times faster than that its conjugate acid analogue under comparable conditions ($k_{\text{cb}}(\text{tzNH})/k(\text{tzNH}_2) = 1.4 \times 10^7$). This is predominantly due to the activation enthalpy difference ($\Delta H^\ddagger = 92 \pm 3 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ for the aquation of tzNH_2 complex) and must be connected with the energetics of σ - and π -bonding of the amido-ligand with cobalt(III) in the transition/initial state of the amido base.

Carboxylato complexes : The carboxylato amineM(III) ($\text{M} = \text{Co}, \text{Cr}, \text{Rh}, \text{Ru}$) complexes undergo both spontaneous and acid catalysed aquation,

The acid-catalysed aquation of maleato- and fumaratopentamminecobalt(III)²⁷, in which the two carboxylate groups are disposed *cis*(A) and *trans*(B) to each other, respectively, show considerable reactivity difference; the former is less prone to acid-catalysis than the latter. This has been ascribed to the effect of internal hydrogen bonding in the maleato complex which does not favour protonation equilibrium of the cobalt(III)-bound carboxylate function. The solvent deuterium isotope effect ($k_{\text{D}_2\text{O}}/k_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$) also support the rapid protonation pre-equilibrium preceding the Co-O bond heterolysis in the acid catalysed path.

The acid-catalysed aquation of bis(tmd)(malonato)cobalt(III) (tmd = 1,3-diaminopropane) is 30 times faster than that of the corresponding ethylenediamine complex. The reactivity difference is believed to owe its origin to the steric effect arising out of the conformational flexibility of the chelate rings. Relatively greater steric acceleration of the six-membered chelate ring of the tmd complex is expli-

cable in terms of the I_d mechanism (Co-O bond breaking)²⁸. The kinetics of the acid-catalysed aquation of (*N*-carboxyphenyliminodiacetato)(glycinato)chromate(III) (CpidaCr^{III}) demonstrated exceptional stability of the tetradentate chelate ring towards protonation and H⁺-catalysed ring opening. In preference, the coordinated glycinate is presumed to undergo a transformation to a bidentate O,O' chelate with dissociation of the amine function in the protonated form²⁹.

Metal ion catalysed aquation of pyridine-2-carboxylatopentaaminecobalt(III) has been reported; the binuclear complexes are involved as the active species³⁰,

Cu^{II} is a better catalyst and it forms stronger complex than Ni^{II} ($k^{\text{Cu}}/k^{\text{Ni}} = 6.0$ at 65°, $\log K_M = 5.8 \pm 0.2$, 4.6 ± 0.1 at 30° for Cu^{II} and Ni^{II}, respectively). The activation enthalpy and entropy data for the catalysed aquation ($\Delta H^\ddagger = 87 \pm 5$, 111 ± 4 kJ mol⁻¹; $\Delta S^\ddagger = -66 \pm 15$, -13 ± 11 J K⁻¹ mol⁻¹ for the binuclear complexes of Cu^{II} and Ni^{II}, respectively) fall in the range of values usually ascribed to Co-O bond cleavage in the carboxylatocobalt(III) complexes. Catalysis of aquation of *cis*-(diformato)bis(ethylenediamine)cobalt(III) by Cu^{II}³¹ is believed to involve a reactive intermediate in which the metal ion is bridged by both the coordinated formate groups. However, the stability constant (K_{Cu}) of the binuclear species was too low to be evaluated. The (dicarboxylato)-(CO₃)chromium(III) and tris(diketonato)ruthenium(III) undergo facile acid-catalysed aquation³². Also the complexes, (malonato)₃Cr(III), (malonato)₂(en)₂Cr(III) are transformed completely to Cr(EDTA)⁻ in the presence of EDTA at suitable conditions³³. The kinetics of these reactions have been investigated and the mechanism has been elucidated. Unexpectedly fast rate of spontaneous aquation of ($\alpha\beta$ S)-(glycinato-*O*)(tetraethylenepentamine)cobalt(III) ($k_{\text{aq}} = 5.4 \times 10^{-4}$ s⁻¹ at 25°) with activation parameters ($\Delta H^\ddagger = 104 \pm 10$ kJ mol⁻¹, $\Delta S^\ddagger = +41 \pm 30$ J K⁻¹ mol⁻¹) comparable to those for similar other substrates, and remarkable inertness of its *N*-protonated analogue to aquation has been accounted for by the internal conjugate base mechanism³⁴,

This complex also undergoes base-hydrolysis with $k_{\text{OH}} = 20.9 \pm 1.3$ dm³ mol⁻¹ s⁻¹ (25°, $I = 0.1$ mol dm⁻³), $\Delta H^\ddagger = 99.4 \pm 1.3$ kJ mol⁻¹, $\Delta S^\ddagger = 114 \pm 4$ J K⁻¹ mol⁻¹ (Ref. 35). The activation parameters for both paths are comparable and are consistent with the conjugate base mechanism involving Co-O bond breaking. Retardation by CO₃²⁻, SO₄²⁻ and acceleration by PO₄³⁻ of the base hydrolysis reaction of this complex also supports the highly polar (ion-pair like) transition state.

Isomerisation reactions

Chakravorty *et al.*³⁶ investigated the *cis-trans* isomerisation of several mixed ligand complexes of Ru(II,III) and Os(II,III) derived from dithiocarbonates (ROCS₂), trithioxamates (RSCS₂), thioxamate (S₂CNEt₂), and Ph₃P. The isomerisation reactions are all redox driven. Kinetics and equilibria were studied by spectrophotometric and cyclic voltametric techniques. The *trans* → *cis* isomerisation of such complexes for the bivalent states of the metal ions is comparatively slower than the *cis* → *trans* isomerisation for the analogous complexes in the trivalent state of the metal ions. Remarkable isomer preference of the *cis* for the bivalent state and *trans* for the trivalent state is an important observation both from kinetic and thermodynamic standpoints. The species, *cis*-[Ru^{III}(S₂(CNEt)₂)(PPh₃)₂]⁺ and *trans*-[Ru^{II}(S₂(CNEt)₂)(PPh₃)₂]⁰ generated in the C.V. experiments are too unstable and spontaneously isomerise (~100%) to the corresponding *trans*- and *cis*-bivalent species, respectively. The factors controlling the geometrically preferred oxidation states have been suggested to be metal-phosphorus π -bonding and Ph₃P---Ph₃P steric repulsion. The isomerisation reactions are believed to proceed via the twist mechanism (intramolecular), the supporting evidence being negative values of ΔS^\ddagger .

In a recent study of the acid and iron(III) catalysed hydrolysis of *trans*-(Hmalonato)bis(ethylenediamine)cobalt(III) Das and Nanda³⁷ reported extensive isomerisation in the product. The *trans* → *cis* isomerisation is believed to occur in the transition state as the kinetics were strictly monophasic involving rapid equilibration of the substrate and Fe^{III} to generate the reactive binuclear intermediate,

The activation entropy for the metal ion catalysed aquation

(which is also the isomerisation reaction) is small negative ($\Delta S^\ddagger = -21 \pm 40 \text{ J K}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$) despite the solvation requirements of the departing groups in the transition state.

Pramanik and Banerjee³⁸ reported the kinetics and mechanism of complex formation of (methyl-2-pyridyl-ketoxime) with iron(II), and the isomerisation of the resulting species. Zn^{II} is a highly labile metal ion in aqueous solution. A stopped flow kinetic study depicting the features of tetrahedral \rightarrow octahedral interconversion of tetracyanozincate(II) to bis(4-(2-pyridyl)azoresorcinol]zinc(II) has been reported by Prasad *et al.*³⁹.

The linkage isomerisation of the *O*-bonded sulfitocobalt(III) species has been investigated⁴⁰. The process is totally intramolecular,

(R = a ligand moiety (or ligand moieties) occupying rest five-coordination position of Co^{III})

The *O*-sulfito complex is produced by SO_2 addition to $\text{Co}^{\text{III}}\text{-OH}$ bond at $\text{pH} < 7$. However, direct SO_3^{2-} substitution with $(\text{tren})\text{CoOH}^{2+}$ leading to $(\text{tren})\text{Co-SO}_3^+$ has been observed in alkaline medium^{41a}.

The resulting complex also undergoes isomerisation at the cobalt(III) centre to alter the arrangement of tren around the metal ion by the strong *trans*-activation of S-bonded sulfite. It is interesting to note that *trans*- $\text{Co}^{\text{III}}(\text{Salen})(\text{OH}_2)\text{-}(\text{SO}_3)$ is the sole product when the corresponding diaquacobalt(III) complex reacts with $\text{SO}_2/\text{HSO}_3^-/\text{SO}_3^{2-}$ buffer in mild acidic medium^{41b}. However, kinetics measurements over extended conditions of pH, temperature and $[\text{S}^{\text{IV}}]_{\text{T}}$ conform to the fact that SO_2 addition to $\text{Co}^{\text{III}}\text{-OH}$ for this complex is rate-limiting which is also concerted with $\text{Co}^{\text{III}}\text{-OSO}_2 \rightarrow \text{Co}^{\text{III}}\text{-SO}_3$ transformation. The photochemical generation of $\text{Co}^{\text{III}}\text{-OSO}_2$ species from several other S-bonded sulfitocobalt(III) complexes have been investigated^{41c}. Contrastingly, a case study of the photochemistry of oxygen and sulfur-bonded (thiosulfato)(tetraethylenepentamine)cobalt(III) in acidic aqueous solution reported by Das *et al.*^{41d} indicates no ligand linkage isomerisation; aquation of the cobalt(III) substrate accompanied by some decomposition of $\text{S}_2\text{O}_3^{2-}$ was observed.

Reactions of coordinated ligands

The transformation of an imine to amide is a fundamental organic reaction. Chakravorty *et al.*⁴² investigated this reaction using certain imine complexes of ruthenium and rhenium. For a typical ruthenium(III)- α -diimine complex this

transformation is shown below :

where

Only one D is oxidised to amide which is coordinated in the deprotonated form. The reaction model involves initial rate-determining H_2O addition to one of the imine function. The carbinolamine intermediate then undergoes fast induced electron transfer (oxidative radical formation), Ru^{III} being reduced internally to Ru^{II} followed by fast reoxidation of the Ru^{II} -amide complex by another $[\text{RuD}_2\text{Cl}_2]^+$ to yield the final product. The rate law for this transformation in dichloromethane-acetonitrile(1 : 6) mixture containing measured amount of H_2O is given by

$$\text{Rate} = k [\text{trans-}\{\text{RuD}_2\text{Cl}_2^+\}][\text{H}_2\text{O}]$$

Values of the rate and activation parameters are : $k(298 \text{ K}) = 1.5 \times 10^{-3} \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$, $\Delta H^\ddagger = 52.3 \pm 3.7 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$, $\Delta S^\ddagger = -125 \pm 12 \text{ J K}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$. The large negative value of ΔS^\ddagger is consistent with associative mechanism and retention of the steric configuration of the parent complex. A crucial reaction condition for this transformation appears to be the easy accessibility of the two oxidation states of ruthenium and the high polarising power of Ru^{III} for the facile H_2O attack at the aldimine function.

Metal ion mediated formation of aldimine complexes from salicylaldehyde (SalH) and primary amines is an important reaction of biological significance. It involves ternary complex of M^{II} , SalH and the primary amine. The ternary complex is then transformed to the imine complex at a rate characteristic of the metal ion and the amine. Dash *et al.*⁴³ reported the kinetics of formation of the ternary complex between Ni^{II} -2-aminomethylbenzimidazole (AMB) and salicylaldehyde and its transformation to the bicyclic imine complex (Ni^{II} coordination occurs by the imine N, pyridine-N of benzimidazole and phenoxide function of Sal^-),

At 25° ($I = 0.3 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$), $k_f = (4.4 \pm 0.4) \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and $k_r = 38.4 \pm 0.4 \text{ s}^{-1}$, $k_{\text{NiL}} = (1.8 \pm 0.5) \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$. The bicyclic imine complex is stable to hydrolysis at $\text{pH} > 6$, under which condition the free imine easily splits up with water indicating marked stabilising effect of metal

gen into the Pd-C bond (metalloxylation) has been effected by *m*-Cl-perbenzoic acid.

The order of the reaction in [*m*-Cl-perbenzoic acid] is 1 while it may be 1 or 2 on the [Pd-C substrate]. In the latter case, the rate-determining step involves two molecules of Pd-C substrate and one molecule of the peracid; the peroxy ligand is believed to bridge the Pd centres. The structure-reactivity correlation has been tested using a series of 2-(alkylsulfinyl)azobenzene ligands and Hammett plot ($\log k$ vs σ) yielded excellent straight-lines consistent with the demands of polar transition state⁵³.

The insertion of small molecules like O₂ and SO₂ into Co-C bond has been investigated by Gupta and Roy⁵⁴. They used organocobaloximes, model for vitamin B₁₂. Oxygen and sulfur dioxide insertion occurs under photochemical conditions. The oxygen insertion involves nonchain free radical reaction, the kinetics of which show first order dependence in both [organocobaloxime] and [oxygen]. The thermal decomposition of the dioxy products in benzene and methanol form the corresponding hydrocarbons and aldehyde/alcohol. The participation of peroxy radicals is confirmed in the decomposition of the dioxy products. The work has a great significance and relevance in view of the existing uncertainty in the mechanism of these reactions⁵⁵. Sulfur dioxide gets readily inserted into Co-C bond under photochemical conditions. Gupta *et al.* established unequivocally that this reaction is not a true insertion reaction but is a consequence of free radical chain process.

Reactions in mixed solvent media

Medium plays a vital role in the studies of rates and mechanisms or reactions. As reactants, products and transition states are solvated, the thermodynamics of solvation controls the thermally activated rate processes. The solvent co-sphere of the initial state (i.s.), transition state (t.s.) and the product state (p.s.) of a reaction are generally assumed to be in thermodynamic equilibrium with the bulk solvent phase. In recent years greater emphasis has been laid on the mixed solvent media comprising mixtures of water and nonaqueous solvents. The aquo-organic solvent systems provide great opportunity to examine the role of solvent structure, polarity, hydrogen bonding and preferential solvation effects on the rates and mechanisms of reactions. Some of the model reactions investigated in the mixed solvent media fall in to the following categories : (i) anation, (ii) solvolysis, (iii) metal ion catalysed hydrolysis.

Anation :

De *et al.* investigated the anation of *cis*-[Co(en)₂(OH₂)₂]³⁺ by glycine⁵⁶, dL-valine⁵⁷, L-serine⁵⁸ and quinolinic acid (pyridine-2,3-dicarboxylic acid)⁵⁹ in aqueous etha-

nol (10 < %v/v EtOH < 30) mixtures. The reactions follow typical ion-pair dissociative interchange mechanism I_d. The rate constant correlates well with the relative permittivity of the medium ($\log k$ vs D_s^{-1} plot is linear). They have, however, observed biphasic kinetics for the anation by quinolinic acid (H₂Qin),

The formation of the intermediate (monobonded form) (k_1) is 40 times faster than its ring closure (k_2) (40–55°, 30% v/v EtOH). The activation enthalpy and entropy for the ring closure step is lower than the same for the formation of the monobonded intermediate ($\Delta H_1^\ddagger/\Delta H_2^\ddagger = 117.2/100.5$; $\Delta S_1^\ddagger/\Delta S_2^\ddagger = 69.4/12.1$). Similar studies have been extended to Cr(OH₂)₆³⁺/Cr(OH₂)₅OH²⁺-L-histidine⁶⁰, iminodiacetic acid⁶¹, salicylaldehyde⁶², *cis*-bis(biguanide)M^{III}(OH₂)₂-aspartic acid⁶³. The dielectric effect is consistent with the ion-pair mechanism I_a for Cr(OH₂)₆³⁺ and I_d for Cr(OH)(OH₂)₅²⁺.

Solvolysis :

The solvolytic aquation/base-catalysed hydrolysis of a series of *cis*-[Co(en)₂BX]²⁺ (B = amine, X = Cl, Br) and related complexes have been investigated by Dash *et al.*⁶⁴ in several aquo-organic solvent media. Nonlabile amine ligand (B) with potential hydrogen bond acceptor/donor sites, aromatic and hydrophobic groups and organic cosolvent + H₂O in the range 0 < % v/v O.S. < 80 (O.S. = protic and dipolar aprotic solvents) have been used. The rate constant-solvent composition profile is generally given by $\log k_{aq}^s = a + b X_{org} + c X_{org}^2$, where X_{org} is mole fraction of the cosolvent. Variations of rate ($\log k_{aq}^s$) with D_s^{-1} (D_s = bulk dielectric constant), solvent ionising parameter (Grunwald-Winstein Y), Dimroth-Richardt polarity index (E_T^N) and acidity and basicity parameters of the mixed solvents in most cases have been found to be nonlinear. Preferential solvation due to electrostatic and hydrophobic interaction effects control the reactivities of the substrates without altering the essential mechanistic features. Also the solvent structure mediated solvation of the initial state and transition state is demonstrated in the nonlinear variation of ΔH^\ddagger and ΔS^\ddagger with X_{org} ; the effects of solvents on these thermo-

dynamic parameters are, however, mutually compensatory, thus signifying the insensitiveness of the mechanism to solvent perturbation.

The decarboxylation of bicarbonatopentaamminecobalt(III), $[(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{CoOCO}_2\text{H}]^{2+}$ (Ref. 65) and SO_2 elimination of *O*-bonded bisulfite complex, $(\alpha\beta\text{S})[\text{Co}(\text{tetren})\text{OSO}_2\text{H}^{2+}$ (indirect solvolysis)(Ref. 66) are intramolecular processes involving associative transition states from which CO_2 and SO_2 depart to the bulk aqueous phase. The solvent effect studies clearly demonstrate substantial control of the media on these unimolecular rate processes although the differential solvent perturbation effects of the $\text{N}_5\text{Co}^{\text{III}}$ moieties in the initial state and transition state are expected to be minimal. The thorough study of the decarboxylation of the bicarbonato complex in aquo-organic solvent media (0–70% wt of cosolvent, $15 < t/^\circ\text{C} < 40$) using MeOH, PrⁱOH, Bu^tOH, EG, AC, AN (acetonitrile), DMSO and EC (ethylenecarbonate) as cosolvents⁶⁵ has revealed the importance of cosolvent specific solvent structural effects on ΔH^\ddagger and ΔS^\ddagger (plots of which against X_{org} display extrema) and preferential solvation of the substrate.

The interesting observations among other details for the base-hydrolysis of $(\text{tetren})\text{Co}(\text{salH})^{2+}$ ($\text{salH}^- = \text{salicylate monoanion}$)⁶⁷ was (i) fast spontaneous aquation of the phenoxide species,

and (ii) remarkable solvent acceleration of the rate of aquation for this species in DMSO + H_2O , AN + H_2O and AC + H_2O . This further established firmly the internal conjugate base mechanism (see above); the pendant phenoxide moiety acted as a stronger base with increasing proportion of the nonaqueous solvent component (the effect being maximum for aprotic cosolvents which do not form H-bonds with the phenoxide moiety) for the internal $\text{NH}\dots\text{O} = \text{N}\dots\text{HO}$ equilibrium generating the reactive amido base. This was further substantiated in another solvent effect study on the base-hydrolysis of (*o*-methoxybenzoato)(tetren)cobalt(III)⁶⁸ which totally lacked the internal conjugate base mechanism. The *o*-methoxybenzoatotetren complex depicted several other interesting features relating to preferential solvation, and solvent structure mediated activation. Initial state and transition state effects could be analysed separately for this complex by combining the solubility data (MeOH + H_2O) with the rate data.

Metal ion catalysed hydrolysis :

Solvent effects on the Cu^{II} -promoted, H^+ -catalysed hydrolysis of bis(acetylacetonatoethylenediimine)copper(II) (Cubaen) has been studied by Gangopadhyay *et al.*⁶⁹ in EtOH + H_2O ($10 < \% \text{ v/v EtOH} < 25$). The rate data have been correlated with the permittivity parameter, $(D-1)/(2D+1)$, solvent ionising power (*Y*), polarity index E_{T}^{N} (or *Z*).

Th^{IV} -catalysed aquation of oxalatopentaamminecobalt(III) have been examined by Dash and Pradhan⁷⁰ using MeOH, PrⁱOH, Bu^tOH and EG as cosolvents. The reactive binuclear species is highly charged with the charge centres separated by the bridging ligand : Surprisingly, the solvent perturbation effects on the aquation rate of the binuclear species (i.e. for the formation of $(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{CoOH}_2^{3+}$ and $[\text{C}_2\text{O}_4\text{Th}]^{2+}$) are only marginal.

Conclusion and prospects

We hope that this short review will make the readers aware of the research activities pursued in our country during the last decade on Inorganic Reaction Mechanisms and related areas. The field is wide open due to variations of metal ions, the ligand systems, time-scales of measurements as also the varieties of reactions which the coordination complexes undergo in gaseous and condensed phases. The study of the substitution reactions of metal ion complexes have led to a general conclusion that the mechanisms fall under the category *A*, *I_a*, *I_d* and *D*. However, the examples of the two extreme cases are rather sparse. There is ample scope for further investigations emphasising on the stereochemical aspects and elucidation of the nature of intermediates involved. The generation/detection of transients and study of their kinetic features by photochemical and other fast reaction technique continue to be an expanding area of research both from academic and technological standpoint and need to be pursued actively in the years ahead. In this respect there is further need to develop infrastructural facilities at several research centres in the country.

The molecular recognition effects on the rates and mechanisms of reactions are some interesting aspects which warrant continued attention. The solvation of inorganic complexes and the importance of such knowledge in understanding their stabilities and reactivities in condensed phase are of considerable value. In particular, the solvation characteristics should help in optimising conditions for inorganic/organometallic reactions and homogeneous catalysis. In this respect reactions in nonaqueous and mixed aqueous solvents should prove to be most rewarding area for continued study.

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References

1. P. A. Treglon in "Mechanisms of Inorganic and Organometallic Reactions", ed. M. V. Twigg, Plenum, New York, 1994, Vol. 9, Chap. 9.
2. M. Eigen and K. Tamm, *Z. Electrochem.*, 1962, **66**, 93.
3. M. C. Ghosh, P. Bhattacharya and P. Banerjee, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1988, **91**, 1.
4. M. M. Taqui Khan, D. Chatterjee, A. B. Boricha, R. R. Merchant, M. A. Moiz and A. Hussain, *React. Kinet. Catal. Lett.*, 1992, **46**, 145; M. M. Taqui Khan, H. C. Bajaj, D. Chatterjee, A. Hussain and M. A. Moiz, *Polyhedron*, 1990, **9**, 2681.
5. A. C. Dash and A. N. Acharya, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci. (Chem. Sci.)*, 1993, **105**, 225.
6. G. Krishnamurthy and B. S. Prabhananda, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci. (Chem. Sci.)*, 1985, **95**, 337.
7. C. C. Deb, D. K. Hazra and S. C. Lahiri, *Z. Phys. Chem. (Leipzig)*, 1986, **267**, 769.
8. K. Sriram, T. Sreelakshmi, L. Ramadevi and C. Ramakrishna, *Int. J. Chem. Kinet.*, 1992, **24**, 919.
9. S. Bandopadhyaya and D. Banerjee, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1994, **71**, 483; A. C. Dash, R. K. Nanda and R. Das, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1991, **30**, 617; A. K. Das, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1994, **33**, 740.
10. H. C. Malhotra and J. Prakash, *Proc. Indian Natl. Acad., Part A*, 1984, **50**, 38, 46; 1987, **53**, 223; H. C. Malhotra and A. K. Jain, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1988, **27**, 246; *Proc. Indian Natl. Acad., Part A*, 1988, **54**, 326, 967; H. C. Malhotra and G. C. Sharma, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1988, **27**, 698; 1989, **28**, 285; *Proc. Indian Natl. Acad., Part A*, 1989, **55**, 686; H. C. Malhotra and A. Kumar, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1994, **35**, 999; *Proc. Indian Natl. Acad., Part A*, 1994, **60**, 419; 1991, **57**, 471; 1992, **58**, 133.
11. A. C. Dash, A. N. Acharya and R. K. Sahoo, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1994, 3727.
12. A. C. Dash, A. N. Acharya and R. K. Sahoo, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1995, **20**, 147.
13. T. Pramanik, A. Das and D. Banerjee, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1991, **16**, 332; A. Das, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1994, **19**, 395.
14. (a) S. P. Chattopadhyaya and D. Banerjee, *Polyhedron*, 1994, **13**, 1981; (b) A. C. Dash, R. K. Sahoo and A. N. Acharya, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1998, **37**, 11; (c) A. N. Acharya, A. C. Dash and S. Das, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1998, **23**, 175.
15. R. Das, N. Das and A. C. Dash, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1995, 3627.
16. (a) A. C. Dash and J. Pradhan, *Int. J. Chem. Kinet.*, 1992, **24**, 155; (b) A. C. Dash, A. N. Acharya and R. K. Nanda, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1991, **30**, 769; (c) A. C. Dash, R. K. Nanda and A. N. Acharya, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1993, 1023; (d) N. Das and R. Das, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1995, **20**, 463; (e) N. Das, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci. (Chem. Sci.)*, 1993, **105**, 245; (f) N. Das and A. C. Dash, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1992, **31**, 678; (g) N. Das, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1993, **18**, 372; (h) A. C. Dash, P. Mohanty and A. N. Acharya, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1995, **20**, 406.
17. (a) P. Misra, R. M. Naik and P. C. Nigam, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1987, **127**, 71; (b) R. M. Naik and P. C. Nigam, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1987, **12**, 261; (c) N. Gupta and P. C. Nigam, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1987, **12**, 463; (d) R. M. Naik and P. C. Nigam, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1985, **10**, 220 T, 227.
18. S. Tripathy and S. Bhattamisra, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1993, 1907.
19. (a) S. Bhattamisra and S. Tripathy, *Monatsh. Chem.*, 1992, **122**, 27; S. Tripathy and S. Bhattamisra, *New J. Chem.*, 1992, **16**, 735; (b) A. C. Dash, A. N. Acharya and R. K. Sahoo, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1996, **21**, 337; (c) A. C. Dash and A. N. Mishra, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1998, **37**, 961.
20. V. Garg, S. Kumar and P. S. Relan, *Oriental J. Chem.*, 1994, **10**, 346.
21. A. Das, S. Gangopadhyaya and D. Banerjee, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1986, **11**, 259.
22. R. M. Naik and P. C. Nigam, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1987, **26**, 205.
23. E. Ahmed, C. Chatterjee, C. J. Cooksey, M. L. Tobe, G. Williams and M. Humanes, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1989, 645.
24. A. C. Dash, N. Dash and J. Pradhan, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1991, 1843.
25. A. C. Dash, R. K. Nanda and A. N. Acharya, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1992, **31**, 747.
26. A. C. Dash and J. Pradhan, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1991, **30**, 601.
27. C. Chatterjee and M. Stephens, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1991, **30**, 1005.
28. C. Chatterjee and S. Das, *J. Coord. Chem.*, 1986, **15**, 147.
29. C. Chatterjee and A. S. Bali, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1987, 2095.
30. N. Das and A. C. Dash, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1993, **32**, 531.
31. A. C. Dash, R. K. Nanda and N. Das, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1987, **12**, 331.
32. B. Chakravorty and S. Adhikari, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1991, **16**, 586.
33. A. N. Rao and V. A. Ramam, *Chim. Acta. Turc.*, 1988, **16**, 233; V. A. Ramam and A. N. Rao, *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. (India)*, 1991, **61**, 141.

34. A. C. Dash, S. Das and R. K. Nanda, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1990, **29**, 227.
35. A. C. Dash and S. Das, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1994, **33**, 1013.
36. (a) A. Pramanik, N. Bag, D. Ray, G. K. Lahiri and A. Chakravorty, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1991, **30**, 410; (b) A. Pramanik, N. Bag, G. K. Lahiri and A. Chakravorty, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1992, 101; (c) A. Pramanik, N. Bag and A. Chakravorty, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1995, 1543; (d) N. Bag, G. K. Lahiri and A. Chakravorty, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1990, 1557; (e) A. Pramanik, N. Bag, G. K. Lahiri and A. Chakravorty, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1990, 3823.
37. N. Das and R. K. Nanda, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1990, **15**, 293.
38. S. T. Pramanik and D. Banerjee, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1994, **33**, 826.
39. S. Prasad, P. C. Nigam and M. Phull, *Int. J. Chem. Kinet.*, 1992, **24**, 239.
40. A. C. Dash and B. Padhy, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1989, **28**, 2054; A. C. Dash, A. A. El-Awady and G. M. Harris, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1981, **20**, 3160.
41. (a) A. C. Dash, A. N. Acharya and A. K. Patnaik, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci. (Chem. Sci.)*, 1995, **107**, 533; (b) A. C. Dash, A. Roy and S. Aditya, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1986, **25**, 207; A. C. Dash, K. C. Jena, A. Roy, D. Mukherjee and S. Aditya, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1997, 2451; (c) A. Das and A. C. Dash, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 2000, 1949; (d) R. Das, N. Das, A. C. Dash, A. Roy and S. K. Sarkar, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1996, **21**, 90.
42. (a) M. Menon, A. Pramanik and A. Chakravorty, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1995, **34**, 3310; (b) M. Menon, A. Pramanik, N. Bag and A. Chakravorty, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1994, **33**, 403; (c) M. Menon, S. Choudhury, A. Pramanik, A. K. Deb, S. K. Chandra, S. Goswami and A. Chakravorty, *J. Chem. Soc., Chem. Commun.*, 1994, 57.
43. A. C. Dash, A. N. Acharya and R. K. Sahoo, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1994, 3727.
44. A. C. Dash, D. Panda and B. Dash, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1984, **25**, 141.
45. A. C. Dash and N. Das, *Polyhedron*, 1995, **14**, 1221.
46. S. Gangopadhyay, R. N. Banerjee and D. Banerjee, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1985, **10**, 310.
47. C. Narayanaswamy, T. Ramasami and D. Ramaswamy, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1986, **25**, 4052.
48. A. C. Dash, S. K. Sarkar, D. Mukherjee and S. Aditya, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1995, **34**, 393.
49. A. K. Mohapatra, D. Bandopadhyay, P. Bandopadhyay and A. Chakravorty, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1986, **25**, 2214.
50. C. Sinha, D. Bandopadhyay and A. Chakravorty, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1988, **27**, 1173.
51. S. Chattopadhyay, C. Sinha, S. B. Choudhury and A. Chakravorty, *J. Organomet. Chem.*, 1992, **427**, 111.
52. C. K. Pal, S. Chattopadhyay, C. Sinha and A. Chakravorty, *J. Organomet. Chem.*, 1992, **439**, 91.
53. C. Sinha, D. Bandopadhyay and A. Chakravorty, *J. Chem. Soc., Chem. Commun.*, 1988, 468.
54. B. D. Gupta and S. Roy, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1985, **108**, 261.
55. B. D. Gupta, M. Roy and S. Roy, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1987, **28**, 1219.
56. D. Chatterjee, K. Bandopadhyay and G. S. De, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1986, **25**, 350.
57. D. Chatterjee and G. S. De, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1988 **61**, 2623.
58. D. Chatterjee and G. S. De, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1987, **12**, 241.
59. K. Banerjee, B. Niyogy and G. S. De, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1987, **12**, 241.
60. H. G. M. Mustofy and G. S. De, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci. (Chem. Sci.)*, 1987, **98**, 255.
61. H. G. M. Mustofy, J. N. Mandal and G. S. De, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1987, **26**, 336.
62. P. De and G. S. De, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1989, **14**, 241.
63. A. K. Ganguly and G. S. De, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1992, **14**, 241.
64. A. C. Dash and N. Dash, *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans. 1*, 1987, 2505; 1988, 75; *Int. J. Chem. Kinet.*, 1989, **21**, 101; A. C. Dash and J. Pradhan, *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans. 1*, 1988, 2387; 1989, 2797; *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1988, **27**, 772; 1990, **29**, 167; A. C. Dash and P. K. Das, *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans. 1*, 1989, 2405; *Int. J. Chem. Kinet.*, 1990, **22**, 307; A. C. Dash, A. N. Acharya and S. Das, *Int. J. Chem. Kinet.*, 1999, **31**, 55; A. C. Dash, A. N. Acharya and J. Pradhan, *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans.*, 1996, 3353; A. C. Dash and S. Das, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1997, **36**, 849; 1999, **38**, 434.
65. A. C. Dash, N. Dash, P. K. Das and J. Pradhan, *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans.*, 1991, 3753; A. C. Dash, R. K. Nanda and S. Aditya in "Facets of Coordination Chemistry", eds. B. V. Agarwala and K. N. Munshi, World Scientific Publishing, Singapore, 1993, Chap. V, p. 56.
66. A. C. Dash, N. Dash, S. Aditya and A. Roy, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1988, **27**, 398.
67. A. C. Dash, G. C. Pradhan and R. Acharya, *Int. J. Chem. Kinet.*, 1995, **27**, 1033; A. C. Dash and P. K. Das, *Int. J. Chem. Kinet.*, 1992, **24**, 165.
68. A. N. Acharya and A. C. Dash, *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans.*, 1994, 3293.
69. S. Gangopadhyay, R. N. Banerjee and D. Banerjee, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1985, **10**, 310.
70. A. C. Dash and J. Pradhan, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1990, **29**, 379.

